

System Usability Scale (SUS) applied to a web-based integrated system for the management of data from people with Parkinson's disease

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Abstract—Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative condition of the central nervous system that affects the brain and brings several different symptoms to the life of patients. Distinct exams can be done to identify and monitor the variety of health problems caused by PD, and each exam can generate a huge quantity of data. Thus, the amount of information produced needs to be managed with organization, security, and consistency. In this work, a system so-called SIDABI was developed to manage data collected from people with PD. The system was made available in institutions that deal with people with PD. The usability of the system was executed by applying the System Usability Scale (SUS). This evaluation tries to bring up possible problems on the system usability and interface. In addition, Fleiss' kappa and Kendall's coefficient were applied to verify the agreement of users. The average SUS score reached 83.0 points, the Fleiss' Kappa was 0.245, a fair concordance, and Kendall's coefficient was 70% of agreement between the raters. These results suggest the system provides a good experience for the user during user interaction.

Keywords—Parkinson's disease, web-based system, data management, System Usability Scale.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative condition of the central nervous system that affects the basal nucleus, bringing on progressive losses of dopaminergic neurons located in the substantia nigra. These neurons produce biochemical substances responsible for important functions, for instance, cognitive behavior, motivation, sleep, humor, memory, motor functions [1], [2].

PD remains without a cure, and its various symptoms can cause injuries that have a direct influence on the patient daily life. Thus, the treatment of the symptoms of PD can help to improve the quality of life of patients.

The most common symptoms caused by PD are tremor, muscular stiffness, slowness of movements (i.e., bradykinesia), changes in gait, changes in handwriting, speech, mood, and cognition (attention, memory, task planning) [3].

Several exams can be carried out to monitor the health condition of a person with PD. The most commons are the electrocardiogram (ECG), that analyzes the electrical activity of the heart, the electromyogram (EMG), used to monitor the muscular electrical activity, and the electroencephalogram (EEG), which allows for the

measurement of the voltage fluctuation of the ionic current of the neurons in the brain. It is also common to the use of image exams (X-ray, tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging). Inertial signals have been used to detect movement patterns through the changes in the inertial states of the individual [1].

All these exams produce a huge amount of information. The data generated need to be stored with security, consistency, accuracy and organized in a way to make future analysis possible.

Aiming to contribute to the management and organization of data collected from people with PD, this research describes the analysis of the usability of a customized system developed for this purpose. The system is able to integrate software modules, for instance, the implementation of clinical scales such as the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale - UPDRS [4].

Usability evaluation is of paramount relevance in the context of human-system interaction. Several examples of evaluation can found in the literature, for instance, Betiol and Cybis [5] applied a usability test using three different approaches to assess a mobile interface, and they could identify a large percentage of usability problems using a questionnaire based on the System Usability Scale (SUS) [6].

Another study used SUS and a User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) to measure the experience and usability in an English learning interface. The estimated score pointed out that all designs were acceptable and usable [7].

In the health area, Coppini et al. [8], used SUS to assess the user acceptance of self-monitoring technology to prevent cardio-metabolic diseases. The work reported SUS scores that confirm the acceptability of the device.

This paper presents the results of the application of SUS to the evaluation of the integrated biomedical data system (SIDABI). The system was in use in different places (hospital, ambulatory and research laboratory) to test its usability.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, 36 judges answered the questionnaire related to the SIDABI system. The questions are based on the System Usability Scale (SUS).

A. System Usability Scale

John Brooke developed the System Usability Scale (SUS) in 1986 as a simple and reliable tool to measure usability. This scale is normally set with ten questions and each one includes five options varying between 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) [6].

The overall SUS score has a range of 0 to 100 points. For this, each option score is subtracted from 1, meaning their range is from 0 to 4. To calculate the final score the value of each odd question (1, 3, 5, 7 and 9) is subtracted from 1. The score of each even question (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10) is calculated as 5 minus the score of the question. The sum of the scores of all ten questions is multiplied by 2.5 to obtain the overall SUS score [6], [9]. An overall SUS score of 68 indicates to us acceptable [7][10].

This work applied SUS because it is free, simple and reliable [9]. This scale was cited in various articles and publications [9]. It was used to assess the usability of SIDABI and detect potential usability problems in the interface. Table 1 shows the questions which were applied.

Table 1 – SUS Questions

Number	Question description
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex.
3	I thought the system was easy to use.
4	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
7	I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use.
9	I felt very confident using the system.
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

B. Evaluation Task

The judges were seated in front of a desktop computer or notebook and then via a web browser, they accessed SIDABI web system to start the task. The entire task took around 10 minutes and 5 minutes to answer the questionnaire. The Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Uberlândia approved the research under protocol 93993118.4.0000.5152.

The executed tasks were: system authentication, navigation to a specific module and its graphical user

interface, record some data, seek for information in the database, upload a file and then log out the system. After that, the judge answered the questionnaire considering the execution of all these tasks.

The first three questions of the questionnaire are not part of the SUS. They are questions to characterize the experience of the user, its age, and time of weekly use of the computer. In addition, the users answered the ten questions in Table 1. The last question was an open question, in which the judge could provide suggestions about improvements in the system.

C. Data analysis

The data collected were converted to a comma-separated value (CSV) format, and then imported to R language script. The package named “IRR” was used to evaluate the inter-rater concordance. In this package, it was used the coefficient Fleiss’ Kappa for multiple raters [11] and Kendall’s coefficient of concordance [12].

Fleiss’ Kappa was proposed by Fleiss in 1971 as a statistic applied to multiple raters or judges based on Cohen’s Kappa that was used only for two raters. In general, Fleiss’ Kappa considers inter-rater reliability in n subjects and r raters per subjects and each judge assigns only one category q to each subject. When the index is close to one there is more concordance between judges and if the result is close to zero it indicates there is a random agreement [11], [13].

Similarly, Kendall’s coefficient is a non-parametric statistic and can be used to measure the agreement among several p judges who are assessing a given set of n objects. Kendall’s index ranges from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (complete agreement) [12].

III. RESULTS

From the first three questions, it was obtained the profile of the raters. The results in Fig. 1 indicates that for question A the predominant age of the judges is around 18 to 25 years old (77.77%). The results of question B shows that the majority (83.33%) of the raters have been using the computer for more than 5 years.

Finally, in Fig. 1 question C, 52.78% of raters spend more than 10 hours per week using a computer, 27.78% spend between 5 and 10 hours per week, and 19.44% of the judges spend around 2 to 5 hours in a computer per week.

Fig. 1: Profile of the raters. Question A represents the age of the judges, B is about the years of computer using, and C illustrates the time spent by the judges in hours per week using a computer.

Fig. 2: Variation of all answers in a comparative boxplot. The mean is highlighted by the red cross.

Fig. 2, illustrates the data variation for each question of SUS in a boxplot. It is possible to note that the odd questions are distributed close to the top of the graph pointing to high values around 3 to 5.

On the other hand, the even questions are in the bottom and close to lower value about 1 to 2. The red point is the position of the data average of each question and the black one shows the outlier values.

The same way, Fig. 3 shows a histogram of answers, a curve of normal distribution and the position of the mean for each question. It is noticed, like in Fig. 2, that the odd questions (green curve) values are near to 4 and 5. However, in the even questions (red curve) the values are close to one and two.

Fig. 3: The histogram of the scores of each question in Table 1. The normal distribution curve is fit on the histogram, in which the green color is related to odd-questions and the red color to even-questions. The mean location is shown by a dashed line in purple color.

Fig. 4: Relation between SUS score and the raters. The value 68 represents the minimum mean of SUS score that is acceptable, and the line at 83 was the mean score obtained in this evaluation.

The alternation between odd and even questions is a characteristic of SUS questionnaire in order to prevent response biases caused by judges not having to think about each statement, by alternating positive and negative items [6], [9].

Fig. 4 illustrates the SUS final score calculated for each rater. In addition, it can be observed the average of 83.0 points represented by a purple dashed vertical line. In SUS score grade, 90 to 100 points is a really great user experience, equivalent to an “A”, 80 to 89 represents a “B”, 70 to 79 is considered a “C” grade, 60 to 69 a “D” and any

value below 59 is considered an “F”. The average in SUS score is 68 points, the green vertical line [10]

The adjective score for SUS was introduced by Bangor, Kortum, and Miller [10]. Thus, a score A is equivalent to “best imaginable” (exactly 100 points), B is “excellent” (85 to 99 points), C is “good” (73 to 84 points), an “Ok” is around 52 to 72 points and values from 51 to 39 points are “poor” and values lower than 25 are “worst imaginable”.

In addition, the Fleiss’ Kappa and Kendall coefficient were estimated to understand the inter-rater agreement. The Fleiss’ Kappa coefficient (K) was 0.245 with a *p-value* of zero, meaning that the agreement between judges is fair according to Landis and Koch [13].

On the other hand, Kendall’s coefficient (W) result was 0.702 and *p-value* 5.9×10^{-44} , suggesting a good agreement among the respondents. In both cases, the *p-value* was smaller than 0.05 showing us that both coefficient values are significantly different from zero. Thereby, allowing us to reject the null hypothesis that there is no agreement among the judges.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the results, the SIDABI was rated with “B” in the SUS scale and obtained a position of “good” and close to “excellent” on the adjective score [10]. This is related to usability factors such as effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction.

Fig. 1 brings an interesting scenario, the judges are young (18-25 years), experienced user if considering the time of use of a computer, and they spend many hours per week in front of the computer. This scenario shows that the judges can have done a meticulous evaluation, contributing to a good and reliable assessment of the system.

The scores showed in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 reflects the alternation between even and odd questions. Questions 2 and 6 obtained the best values and they suggest that the system has low complexity and inconsistency, respectively.

Questions 1 and 5 (Fig. 3) represent the satisfaction in using the system, and the integration of functions of the system, respectively. The obtained mean was about 3.7 and 3.9, suggesting it is necessary to improve this feature.

The SIDABI system obtained very good usability scores as shown in Fig. 4. The majority of the judges scored more than 68 points, which is the minimum acceptable average of the SUS. Only 7 judges rated below the required average, and twenty scored over 83 points. This confirms a good evaluation of the system.

Despite the reasonable agreement showed by Fleiss’ Kappa coefficient, the agreement was further confirmed by Kendall’s using, which was larger than 70% of agreement between raters.

In addition, some suggestions for the improvement of usability were given in the descriptive field (the last question of the questionnaire). These questions suggest the need for correction in some error messages; change the color of all modules to the same color; change validation fields of some forms; to add some fast help in some screens.

The next steps are to improve the system considering the suggestions and corrections to bring more usability and reliability to SIDABI users. In the future, a new test can be

done, by including expert judges with experience in usability principles.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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